

FEATURES OF MILITARY AND PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUTH

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the peculiarities of the military-patriotic education of youth.*

Keywords: *military and patriotic education, youth, love for the motherland, educational system, traditions, scientific outlook.*

In the era of globalization, the problems associated with the spiritual and moral education of young people are among the most important, on the solution of which the future of each state depends. Today, peculiar processes are taking place in international politics. In interstate relations, the method of "influencing the other" has moved into the most difficult stage - the spiritual one. Now states are liquidated by other states not with the help of weapons, strength, wealth, but with the help of spiritual and ideological movements.

Along with the ongoing policy of peace, the Republic of Uzbekistan undertakes to ensure the security, peace and stability of its citizens. He exercises the right to inviolability in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations, at the level of mental adequacy provides military and defensive power.

Military-patriotic education in higher and secondary specialized educational institutions is one of the important activities of our state. Love for the motherland is one of the age-old virtues of the national character of our people. The preservation and improvement of these valuable human qualities should become the main direction of raising our children as worthy sons and daughters of an independent and democratic Uzbekistan.”

At present, the content and process of military-patriotic education is being updated taking into account the development of the educational system of educational institutions of the Republic, the intensification of the socio-economic development of the country, and the growth of the place of the human factor in the defense of the Motherland. Rethinking the preparation of young people for the defense of the Motherland requires the full use of the content, organizational and methodological aspects of military-patriotic education. It is necessary to choose and consolidate traditional forms that are given and tested by analyzing the effectiveness of educational activities, the practice of military-patriotic education, the search for new forms that will more fully realize the tasks of preparing young people for the defense of the Motherland. In modern conditions, they should be enriched with traditions that arose during fundamental changes in society. In recent years, certain work has been done in the country in the field of training conscripts in military-technical specialties, the formation of a spiritually rich and physically healthy personality, and favorable conditions have been created for playing sports, including its technical and applied types. Preparing young people for service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a national task. When solving this problem, pre-conscription initial training, including civil protection, is a mandatory subject in the curriculum. Youth is the future of our Motherland, our nation.

Since we entrust them with the fate of our Motherland, first of all, they must fully understand the complex and responsible task entrusted to them, and make their contribution to it.

After all, love for the Motherland, love for it is directly determined by the creative work of everyone in the development of this country. The adopted Concept of the military-patriotic education of youth is aimed at strengthening the measures taken together with local government bodies to ensure the unity of the army and the people, makes it possible to staff the ranks of our national army with young people with modern knowledge, skills and professional skills, strong will and active citizenship.

One of the most significant enduring values, the ideological basis of the viability of the state is patriotism. The problem of military-patriotic education of the younger generation, due to its potential significance in society, is one of the most urgent in society, since youth is the most fertile time for instilling a sacred sense of love for the Motherland. Military-patriotic education is understood as the gradual and steady formation of love for their homeland among students, which is one of the most important features of a comprehensively developed personality. The understanding of patriotism has a deep theoretical tradition that goes back centuries. Already Plato has reasoning that the motherland is more precious than father and mother. The ideas of patriotism are found in military-historical documents and chronicles as early as the 11th century. The renewal of the state idea takes place at the beginning of the 13th century, and “service to the Fatherland and one’s neighbors” becomes one of the main principles.

To improve the system of military-patriotic education, the formation of a high patriotic consciousness among the citizens of Uzbekistan, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the fundamental improvement of the system for increasing the spiritual and educational level of the military personnel of the armed forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan” was adopted. State programs have been developed and are being implemented: "Patriotic education of citizens", which are aimed at improving the system of patriotic education, primarily in general educational organizations.

The modern understanding of military-patriotic education as one of the priority areas of activity of state institutions is presented in the "Concept of the Military-Patriotic Education of Youth". It formulated the goal - "the development of citizenship, patriotism among students as the most important spiritual, moral and social values, the formation of professionally significant qualities, skills and readiness for their active manifestation in various spheres of society, especially in the process of military and other her, types of public service, fidelity to constitutional and military duty in peacetime and wartime, high responsibility and discipline.

Important components of the theory of military-patriotic education of school youth are: the requirements for high school students in the process of their preparation for the defense of the Fatherland, tasks, basic principles and content. An analysis of the psychological and pedagogical literature makes it possible to identify the following basic requirements for preparing young men for the defense of the Fatherland. A modern warrior must have a whole range of personal qualities, which include ideological, political, moral-psychological, military-technical, physical, as well as the ability to mobilize them in case of military danger. They must be formed in the process of educational activities at school and in the family.

According to S. A. Aliyeva, military-patriotic education has the following specific tasks:

- the formation of a scientific worldview, a system of moral qualities, norms, principles and beliefs among high school students, the development of moral motives for the conscious and conscientious performance of military duty in peacetime and wartime;

- equipping high school students with knowledge about the essence, content, nature, types and causes of modern wars, the features and methods of conducting modern military operations, the use of the latest weapons and military equipment;

-study by high school students of the military-political situation in the world, in neighboring regions, the internal political situation in the country, as well as state policy in the field of ensuring security and armed defense of the country on the basis of the Constitution, military doctrine, existing laws and general military regulations;

- education of patriotism, a sense of duty and personal responsibility for the security of the country, readiness for self-sacrifice in the name of its defense; the fight against immorality, drug addiction, anti-army propaganda and other negative phenomena;

- education on the heroic traditions of the past and present, the development of such qualities as honor, valor, courage, friendship, military comradeship, team building into a single, friendly organism, united by the common goal of serving the Fatherland, collective feelings of military duty;

- fostering respect for the laws, for the requirements of charters and commanders in the spirit of high diligence and discipline, the ability to resist fear, panic, rumors, to show restraint, will and skill in the necessary actions.

Thus, in modern conditions, when the military situation in the world has changed significantly, the socio-economic situation in the country, the army, the school, the study of the theoretical foundations of the military-patriotic education of high school students has shown the need to preserve, implement and creatively develop the pedagogical principles previously laid down in the system of military -patriotic education of young students.

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